

Healthy cattle slaughtered above 8 years of age should continue to be tested for BSE in Germany

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In the entire European Union, hardly any cattle now become ill due to BSE. Thus in Germany the last case of BSE was detected in the year 2009. Against the background of this positive epidemiological trend, a discussion is currently ongoing in the EU whether the mandatory BSE testing regime of healthy slaughtered cattle could be relaxed or abolished entirely. In this connection, the European Food Safety Authority published an Opinion in October 2012 in which the consequences of the existing testing regime are modelled.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute (FLI) are of the opinion that all healthy cattle slaughtered aged older than eight years (96 months) should continue to be systematically tested in order to record cases of atypical BSE and to recognise a potential new epidemic as early as possible.

The full version of the BfR Information in German is available on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/gesund-geschlachtete-rinder-ueber-8-jahre-sollten-in-deutschland-weiter-auf-bse-getestet-werden.pdf>